

AGRICULTURAL SCIENCES

DEFINITION OF THE PESTS' SORT STRUCTURE IN POTATO SOWINGS OF THE WESTERN REGION OF THE AZERBAIJAN REPUBLIC

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Abstract

Growing of the potato plant in the western region of the Azerbaijan Republic for more than 200 years caused collection of the representatives in the fauna and flora concerning the different sorts in agroecosystem. An aim of the research is to work out fight measures integrated to the local condition against the pests in potato sowings of the zones above sea-level, specifying a sort structure, spreading area and biological features of the pests. The route observation-calculation works were performed by involving 30 % of agroecosystem for specifying the pests' sort structure in potato sowings of the western region in 2003-2022. Our researches showed that 31 sorts of the pests spread in potato sowings which are grown in the zones 850-900 meters above sea-level (*Gryllotalpa gryllotalpa* L., *Gryllus desertus* Pall., *Doclostaurus maroccanus* Thnb., *Chaetocnema breviscula* Fald., *Leptinotarsa decemlineata* Say., *Anisoplia leucaspis* Cast., *Melolontha pectoralis* Germ, *Agriotes gurgistanus* Fald and others). An injury of the pests involves underground (mole cricket and wire worms) and surface (Colorado beetle and its larva) organs. 27 sorts of the pests were revealed in agroecosystem while descending 900-1000 meters above sea-level. During the researches aren't found in the zones above 1000 meters. Change of the pests' sort structures depending on geographical zone was determined.

Keywords: potato plant, Colorado beetle, mole cricket, bioecological features.

Introduction

A comparative analyses with the reference information of the research works about sort structure, spreading area, bioecological features and injury of the injurious organisms which assumes negative farming importance extended in agroecosystem besides agrotechnical measures in growing of potato plant, getting of the reach and high harvest. (Kakharov, 2008; Naumova, 2008; Kapustkin, 2009; Zamalieva, 2013. Fisechko, R.N. 2013). There is a great importance of revealing the new sorts which have negative farming importance in harvest preserving (Gerasimova et al., 2007; Anisimov, 2009; Maluga et al., 2013). It is impossible to fight against the pests in an optimal period not studying the sort structure, biology, ecological features, spreading area and other factors of the injurious organisms (Doljenko and Burkova, 2007; Brechko, 2012; Goncharov et al., 2013; Ulyanenko et al., 2015). An analysis of the researches from the reference data shows that injurious organisms more than 100 injure in potato agroecosystem (Vilkova, 2005). But depending on geographical zone the sort structure of the injurious organisms and injuring limit change. The researches show that change of the sort structure and injuring of the pests in agroecosystem is connected with the ecological factors (Bale et al, 2002) . While the microclimate condition that is formed as a result of the ecological factors is fit for the pests the harvest loss happens (Goehring and Oberhauser, 2002; Hodkova and Hodek, 2004; Kosta and Simek, 2000). The seed potato nodule brought from Lvov province (zone of the Ukraine State) was firstly observed in the west region of the republic of Azerbaijan in 1972. At present the pests spread in all the regions of our republic. The Colorado beetle is considered the most dangerous pest not only for the potato

plant but also some more agricultural plants (tomato, aubergine, pepper) (Cannaert, 2011; Yocum, 2001). The various means are used in fight with the pests (pesticides, radiation, gene-modified potato sorts and etc.) (Danks, 2005; Denlinger, 2002; Chen et al., 2004). Being young of the pest from phylogenetic point of view, high ecological plasticity and richness of the nutrient cause mass increase of the Colorado beetle (increase of the population density), it needs for new fight measure preparation against the pest (Arnott and Yan, 2002; Bosa, 2005). An analysis of the statistical indications shows that an arable area of the potato plant (2003-184; 2015-177,6; 2022-178,8 thousand hectares), production volume (2003-1228,3; 2015- 1178,6; 2022- 1089,5 thousand tons), and productivity (2003-153; 2015- 149; 2022-145 cent/ h) decreased under the pests' influence. One of the pests in potato sowings is mole cricket. This pest gnaws firstly planted nodules and developing shoot of the plant, then newly formed nodules seriously during a season (Huseynov, 2012). The wire worms in the potato sowings deteriorate a quality of the marketable produce indications.

Materials and methods

The route observation – account works in the zones above sea-level have been performed for 3 times a month to specify the sort structure of the pests spreading in potato sowings of the western region of the Azerbaijan Republic. They involve 10 % of the arable areas. The surface and underground organs of the plants were looked through during the observations. With this purpose 20 samples and 5 plants in each sample have been examined going in a direction of the arable area diagonal, the observed pests have been gathered in the pots and their account has been performed, a sort structure

of the gathered samples has been specified (Fasulati, 1971).

The hollows were dug by 16 numbers of calculation per hectare in a direction of the area diagonal for specifying the sort structure from the pests on the soil layer. The hollows were dug at 30 cm x 80 cm x 45 cm of size (noticing inter- row of the potato plant). The hollow depth corresponded to the layers (10; 20; 30; 45 cm). The dug soil samples were sieved from the special sieves on the tarpaulin. The observed pests were collected in the testing glass, a table which shows a region, date of revealing pests was pinned on it. The pests investigated as a result of the research were brought to the laboratory and fixed a sort structure (Kosova and Poliakov, 1958).

Definition of the pests in the potato sowings which are grown in the zones above sea-level was performed in the following rules.

1. An injuring percentage of the plants was calculated by the following formula (1).

$$P = \frac{n \cdot 100}{N} \quad (1)$$

Here: P- nodule, shoot and injuring percentage of the leaves, %;

n – injured nodule, shoot and leaves number, number;

N- examined nodule, shoot and a total number of the leaves;

A coefficient turning into 100 %.

2. An injuring intensity of the plants was established over the scores. At this time six-score scale was used.

0 score – plant or organs no injured;

I score- plant or organs were injured till 5 %;

II score – plant or organs were injured till 25 %;

III score – plant or organs were injured from 25 % to 50 %;

IV score – plant or organs were injured from 50 % to 75 %;

V score - plant or organs were injured more than 75 %.

3. An average –score of the injuring intensity was calculated by the following –formula (2):

$$R = \frac{\sum(a \cdot b)}{N} \quad (2)$$

Here: R – average-score of the injuring intensity, score;

$\sum$ - sign of sum

(a ········· b) -injurious organ or plants quantity (a), is multiplied injuring score (b), num./ score.

N- injured organ or a total number of plants , num;

4. A injuring degree of plant or its organs are fixed by the following formula (3).

$$X = \frac{\sum(a \cdot b) \cdot 100}{N \cdot K} \quad (3)$$

Here: X –injuring degree of the plants or organs, %;

$\sum$ - sign of sum;

a – injurious organ or plants quantity, num;

b – corresponding score of injure , score;

N – quantity of the examined plant or organs, num;

K – the highest score of injure, score;

A coefficient turning into 100 %.

The potato nodules in 20 samples (in plant) in a diagonal direction of the hospital area chosen at the end of the season were examined to determine the potato nodules injured by the soil pests. A percentage of the potato nodules injured by the soil pests (mainly mole cricket and wire worms), an average-score of injurious intensity, injurious degree were calculated as above-mentioned forms (Fasulati, 1971).

Discussion

The route observation-account works were carried out in Goranboy, Samukh, Ganja, Goygol, Shamkir, Dashkasan, Gadabay, Tovuz, Gazakh and Aghstafa districts of the region for specifying the pests' sort structure in the potato sowings of the western region of the Azerbaijan.

A height of the region from sea-level and landscape zones were investigated to specify reasons of the change in a sort structure of the pests. A height of the region from sea-level (Baltic sea) changes by 69 meters (Samukh region) and 2470 meters (Shamkir district, Goygol station). Strong change of the height from sea-level over horizontal zonality exerted a serious influence on pests' sort structure in potato sowings.

More than 67 % of the region were distributed between the foothill, partially low mountainous forest-field (from 500 m to 800 – 1000 m) landscape stripe and mean upland half-field (from 1000 m to 2000 m, partially high) landscape. The foothill half-field (from 200 m-to 500-600 m) gains the second place for the landscape stripe zone.

The forming ecological condition – abiotic, biotic, hydro- edaphic, heliophysics, geographic and anthropogenic factors influence the insects' development directly and complexly. The Colorado beetle, *Gryllotalpa*, wire worm, potato tuber moth, autumn bollworm , marble insects larva and others are found in potato sowings in the zones above 850-900 m of sea-level (Table 1).

A reason of not observing *Gryllotalpa gryllotalpa* L., *Chaetocnema breviscula* Fald., *Lygus pratensis* L., in potato agrocenosis, while ascending higher than 900-1000 m of sea-level is the environment being formed by the vertical zonality. The Colorado insect in the potato areas grown till 900-1000 m above sea-level gives three generations (Huseynov, 2012). But decrease of the pests' generations quantity is observed while the height rises. Its reason is a low temperature. So, while the height rises above sea-level a temperature of the air falls 0,6 °C on average. Its reason is a change of the falling angle of the Sun beam. The air temperature falling while growing height exerts influence on other ecological factors. Consequently, the microenvironment plays an important role in biotope formation. Therefore the changes are observed in bioecological characters of

the pests over the vertical zonality (Mammadova et al., 2011).

Table 1.

Sort structure of the pests from insect classes and arthropoda type (Arthropoda) in early and summer potato agrocenosis grown in the zone above 850-900 meters of sea-level of the western region in Azerbaijan

Group	Subgroup	Family	Latin names of the insects	Plant injuring, %		
				Casual	Periodic	Constant
Orthoptera	Dolichocera	Gryllotalpidae	<i>Gryllotalpa gryllotalpa L.</i>			11,6
			<i>Gryllotalpa unispina Sauss.</i>			23,0
	Gryllidae	<i>Gryllus desertus Pall.</i>		2,0		
	Brachycera	Acrididae	<i>Dociostaurus maroccanus Thnb.</i>		1,0	
Coleoptera	Poliphaga	Chrysomelidae	<i>Chaetocnema breviscula Fald.</i>		7,0	
			<i>Leptinotarsa decemlineata Say.</i>			35,0
		Scarabaeidae	<i>Anisoplia leucaspis Cast</i>		2,0	
			<i>Melolontha pectoralis Germ</i>	1,0		
		Elateridae	<i>Agriotes gurgistanus Fald</i>			9,0
			<i>Agriotes sputator L.</i>			-
	Adephaga	Carabidae	<i>Zabrus tenebrioides Goeze</i>		1,0	
		Gelechiidae	<i>Phthorimaea operculella L.</i>			40,0
Tylenchida	Tylenchidae	Various nematodes	<i>Heterodera rostoshiensis Woll.</i>	0,1		

The temperature decreases while the height rises above sea-level, and this causes change of the individual's way out of wintering depending on sea-level. This affects on the Colorado beetle's birthrate and it is a reason for two and least birthrate in the zones higher than 100 m above sea-level.

The changes in spreading and development of the pests observed in agrocenosis are supervised at a height of 500 m above sea-level, at 500-700 meters, 700-900 meters and higher than 1000 meters. And this shows that the ecological factors can create the environment (cenosis) for biotope formation at the noted heights. So the microclimate changes for development of the pests and potato plant at the shown height (Humbatov, 2011). Becoming wild, abnormal development of the early potato sowings 500-700 m above sea-level and spring sowings of the zone 500 m above sea-level are observed. At a height of 700 – 900 m a spreading area of the mole cricket in potato agrocenosis becomes limited. Decrease of the Colorado beetle generations' quantity is revealed at a height more than 1000 m (Gulieva and Safarova, 2013).

As is seen from the researches the relief of the western region is very complicated. The different heights above sea-level are found in some districts (Goygol, Shamkir, Goranboy). Our researches showed that the Colorado beetle in potato agrocenosis of the

Goranboy regions gives two or three generations during a season depending on a height above sea-level. Besides the districts of the same region where the mole cricket spread, there are agrocenoses in which pests don't spread. An impact of increase of the height above sea-level on wire worms population density was revealed. So, it is observed that the population density descends while the height rises. From this point of view, the region can be divided into four half -zones for the "dangerousness degree" depending on the height above sea-level: I half-zone – 700-900 m height above sea-level, II – 900-1000 m ; III – 500 and 500-700 m height. A reason of 700-900 m height above sea-level belonging to I half-zone is richness of the injurious organisms' sort structure, performing the spring sowings in agrocenoses. Three generations of the Colorado beetle, one generation of the mole cricket from the primary pests develop in the spring sowings at a shown height. Besides it, a negative impact of the ecological factors causes abnormal development in the potato root bulbs and this is a reason of the strong decrease in productivity.

For the purpose of the primary pests investigation of the percentage, intensity and degree of the damage in potato plant were specified. It was determined that the Colorado beetle and its larva injured the leaves of

the potato sorts 35,0 % on average . The plant was injured by I-V score and its injurious degree was 13,9 %. The calculation for investigation of the mole cricket injury on green mass of the potato plant showed that the shoots injurious was 13,0 % on average. At the end of the season injuring of the potato bulbs by the mole cricket and wire worms was specified.

The research works showed that the potato bulbs injuring by mole cricket was 23,0 %, by wire worms was 7,0 % (Mammadova and Huseynov, 2010). The product loss was studied to define wide-spread of the pests and their negative farming importance. The researches showed that injuring of the plants by the Colorado beetle till 35,0 % times more than expense spending on chemical fight (was shown in economical-injurious limit).

It was known that a weight of the potato bulb injured by 100 wire worms is 17,6 kg, but a weight of the potato bulb injured by mole cricket is 15,2 kg. It was determined that a weight of 100 health potato bulb is 17,9 kg. The wire worms were a reason for 0,3 kg loss, but mole cricket was a reason for 2,7 kg of the product loss. Injuring of the plant shoots by the potato tuber moth was 22,0 % , but the leaves spreading was 9,0 % in summer sowings (Huseynov, 2003). The potato bulbs infected by the potato tuber moth under the storehouse condition become worthless because of loss in sowing material, food and marketable quality and aren't used for any purpose (Table 2). As is seen from Table 2 the population density rises if there is no any fight against the primary pests, and this may be a reason for the product loss and it can make condition for phytosanitary state every year.

Table 2.

Population density of the primary pests and plants infection

Name of pests	Quantity of the dug hollows	Population density of the pests	Quantity of the samples	Injurious percentage of the plants, %			Weight of the potato bulbs, kg		Product loss	
				shoots	leaves	tubers	health	injurious	kg	%
mole cricket	16	1,6	100 plants	13		–	–	–	–	–
			100 potato tubers	–	–	23	17,9	15,2	2,7	11,4
wire worms	16	1,3	100 potato tubers	–	–	7	17,9	17,6	0,3	4,5
Colorado insect	-	107	100 plants	–	352	–	180	73	107	40,5
potato tuber moth	-	-	100 potato tubers	–	–	100	17,9	16,2	100 % seless	–
			100 plants	22	9,0	–	145	68	77	53,1

Studying bioecological characters of the Colorado beetle in the investigative zone, A graphics depending on temperature of the Colorado beetle's going out of wintering was compiled and depending of the Colorado beetle development on ecological factors in the potato sowings from the zones 900-1000 m above sea-level shown on bioclimogram (Figure 1). As is seen from the

bioclimogram the precipitations quantity changes 20-60 mm for the pests development. But being more of the rainfalls quantity than these parameters (look at soil-climate condition) causes the best environment for the Colorado beetle development. One generation development continue 48-55 days.

Figure 1. Bioclimogram of the Colorado beetle in the potato sowings of the zones till 900-1000 m above sea-level (Goygol district, Gizilgaya settlement)

The bioclimogram of the Colorado beetle development dependence on ecological factors was shown on Figure 2 (in the potato sowings 1000 m above sea-level). A quantity of the precipitations in the zones

1000 m above sea-level is more and it causes lasting of the Colorado beetle's development period. One generation development continued 65-70 days.

Figure 2. Bioclimogram of the Colorado beetle in the potato sowings of the zones higher than 1000 m from sea-level. (Gadabay ditrict, Slavyanka village)

An application of the limited factors in generating ability (generations' quantity) showed that after a height of 900-1000 m sea-level a low temperature of the soil in spring causes late going out of the wintering insects in various depth of soil. The researches show

that the mature individuals of the Colorado beetle spend winter in the deepest layers of soil, while rising up from sea-level. But gradual heating of the soil layer delays going out of the insect in spring (Table 3).

Table 3.

Factual and prognosticating period of the Colorado insect's going out of wintering in the potato sowings from the zones till 900-1000 m above sea-level in the western region (2003-2022)

Years	Soil temperature in 20-30 cm of depth, C ⁰	Beginning date of going out of wintering, date		Difference between factual and prognosticating dates, day
		factual	prognosticating	
2003	16,0	10 May	13 May	+ 3
2004	14,8	24 April	22 April	- 2
2005	16,0	16 April	17 April	+ 1
2006	17,0	04 may	07 may	+ 3
2007	14,3	28 April	25 April	- 3
2008	14,7	24 April	22 April	- 2
2009	14,3	28 April	25 April	- 3
2010	14,8	22 April	22 April	0
2011	17,0	04 may	07 may	+ 3
2012	16,2	18 April	17 April	- 1
2013	15,9	19 April	18 April	- 1
2014	16,0	16 April	17 April	+ 1
2015	15,1	20 April	19 April	- 1
2016	15,7	16 April	15 April	- 1
2017	14,3	28 April	25 April	- 3
2018	14,7	24 April	22 April	- 2
2019	14,8	24 April	22 April	- 2
2020	15,9	19 April	18 April	- 1
2021	16,2	18 April	17 April	- 1
2022	15,7	16 April	15 April	- 1
On average	15,3	18 April	18 April	-

Conclusion

1. The researches show that the landscape stripes play an important role besides the climate stripes in spreading of the pests from zonality standpoint. Dividing of the western region into four half-zones depending on sea-level causes protection of the potato plant from injurious organisms besides providing a good soil-climatic situation for its development. The researches showed that 31 sort pests in the potato sowings at a height till 900 m from sea-level, but 27 sort pests developed in the zones at a height more than 900 m. Among these pests the Colorado beetle, *Gryllotalpa gryllotalpa* L. and *Gryllotalpa unispina* Sauss., nine sort of the wire worms are primary pests.

2. The half-zones of the western region are divided into three groups according to "dangerousness degree" from product loss standpoint: more product is subjected to loss at a height of 700-900 m from sea-level (I group) for "dangerousness degree". So, the spring sowings of the potato plant are performed at a shown height. The potato plant vegetation involves April – August months. The primary pests in this half-zone (Colorado beetle, mole cricket, wire worms) have full development cycle and this rises product loss and pesticide load.

II group - spring sowings of the potato in the zones higher than 900 m from sea-level. The potato spring sowings involve an end of April and August but the beginnings of September. An ecological condition is good for potato plant in these zones. The Colorado beetle develops in two generations, but the mole cricket isn't found in the potato sowings.

III group – early potato sowings in the zones till 500 m above sea-level. The early potato sowings involve the second ten-day and the first half of June. This period is fit for the potato plant development ecologically. Besides it 1,0 -1,5 generation of the Colorado beetle and wintering individuals of the mole cricket develop in early potato sowings, this causes minimizing of the product injury in connection with the pests incomplete development. The summer sowings of the potato grown in the zones till 700 m above sea-level belong to III group. The summer sowings of the potato plant involve the second half of July and November. Relatively decrease of the temperature, falling dew, (or intensifying of the rainfalls), increase of the relative humidity make a good optimal situation for the plant development and this results in increase of productivity at a period of bulbs formation in the summer sowings. At the same time many parts of the development period in the potato bulbs are found in the period of the third generation of the Colorado beetle, mole cricket and wire worms larva 's going to wintering, this causes the product damage.

An adaptation of the sowing period (early, summer, spring sowings) to the local conditions and season causes decrease of the cost price for the fight against the product increase and primary pests.

References

1. Anisimov B.V. 2009: *Protection of the potato from diseases, pests and weeds*. Collection of scientific works by Belov G.L. and others M., "Potato culture", 272 pp.
2. Arnott S.E., Yan N.D. 2002: The influence of drought and reacidification on zooplankton emergence

- from resting eggs. – *Ecological Applications*. 12:138–153
3. Bale J.S., Masters G.J., Hodkinson I.D. et al. 2002: Herbivory in global climate change research: direct effects of rising temperature on insect herbivores. – *Global Change Biology*. 8: 1–16
 4. Bosa C.F. 2005: *Pheromone-mediated communication disruption in Guatemalan potato moth, Tectia solanivora (povolny)*. Swedish university of agricultural Sciences : 29
 5. Brechko E.V. 2012: Optimization of the insecticides application in protection of potato from Colorado insect. – *Guarding and quarantine of plants* . 4:33-37
 6. Cannart F. 2011: Three years of wireworms monitoring with pheromone traps in France. – *IWGO Newsletter*. 31:41-43
 7. Chen B., Kayukawa T., Jiang H. et al. 2004: Trypsin, a novel clip-domain serine proteinase gene up-regulated during winter and summer diapauses of the onion maggot. – *Delia radicum*. Gene.:115–123
 8. Danks H.V. 2005: How similar are daily and seasonal biological clocks. – *Journal of Insect Physiology*: 609–619
 9. Denlinger D.L. 2002: Regulation of diapause. – *Annual Review of Entomology*. 47:93–122
 10. Doljenko V.I., Burkova L.A. 2007: Modernizing of the means and protection technologies of potatoes from pests. – *Agro XXI*. 7-9:15-18
 11. Fasulati K.K. 1971: *Field investigation of the surface invertebrates* .Moscow, High school, 423 pp.
 12. Fisechko R.N. 2013: Peculiarities of the Colorado insect's biology under forest steppe conditions. – *Guarding and quarantine of plants*. 10:42-43.
 13. Gulieva N.F., Safarova I.M. 2013: *Insects ecological physiology*. Baku, Bayramoglu, 285 pp.
 14. Gerasimova A.V., Zenkevich S.V., Lisov A.K. and others . 2007: Integrated guarding of potato. – *Protection and quarantine of plants*. 7:44-46
 15. Goncharov N.P., Ulyanenko L.N., Filipas A.S. and others. 2013: Economical efficiency of the integrated system of the potato seed planting protection in Kaluga region. In: *Materials of the 6th International scientific practical Conference “Agrotechnical method of the plants protection from injurious organisms”*. Krasnodar , June 17-21. pp. 225-231.
 16. Goehring, L., Oberhauser K.S. 2002: Effects of photoperiod, temperature, and host plant age on induction of reproductive diapause and development time in *Danaus plexippus*. – *Ecological Entomology*, 27:674–685
 17. Huseynov K.G. 2003: Working out of the fight measures against the soil pests in potato sowings of the Ganja-Gazakh . – *IPPTGR annual account* : pp.22
 18. Humbatov A.M. 2011: *Entomology . Insect ecology and fight methods against injurious insects*. III Part. Baku, 105 pp.
 19. Huseynov K.G. 2012: Pests sort structure from vertical zonality standpoint in potato sowings of the Ganja-Gazakh region. – *Scientific works of ASAU*. 3:19-22
 20. Huseynov K.G. 2012: Dependence of the period of potato sowings on vertical zonality. – *Agrarian Russia*. 6: 13-17
 21. Hodkova M., Hodek I. 2004: Photoperiod, diapause and cold-hardiness. – *European Journal of Entomology*. 101:445–458
 22. Kapustkin D.V. 2009: *Biological peculiarities of the Colorado insect . Leptinotarsa decemlineata Say. (Coleoptera. Chrysomelidae) in the North- West region of Russia*. Ph. D diss., Sankt-Peterburg ,Pushkin, 219 pp.
 23. Kakharov K.Kh. 2008: *Biological peculiarities of the Colorado insect 9Leptinotarsa decemlineata Say) and measures of the fight against them under Tajikistan conditions*. Ph.D diss. Dushanbe. 240 pp.
 24. Kosta V., Simek, P. 2000: Overwintering strategy in *Pyrrhocoris apterus* (Heteroptera): the relations between life-cycle, chill tolerance and physiological adjustments. – *Journal of Insect Physiology* 46:1321–1329
 25. Kosova B.B., Poliakov I.Y. 1958: *Prognosis of the primary pests and diseases of the agricultural plants*. Moscow, 626 pp.
 26. Mammadova S.R. and Huseynov K.G. 2010: Colorado potato beetle and fight against it. – *Scientific works of ASAU*. 1:34-38
 27. Maluga A.A., Chulikova N.S., Omelchenko N.A. 2013: Selection of the optimal period for potato processing against the Colorado insect. – *Protection and quarantine of plants*. 6:34-36
 28. Mammadova S.R., Huseynov K.G. , Ibrahimov D.E. 2011: Ecological plasticity of the Colorado insect under Ganja-Gazakh conditions of Azerbaijan. – *Head agronomist*. 9:45-47
 29. Naumova N.I. 2008: *Colorado insect and potato guarding from pests under various conditions of land use in North-West of Russia Federation*: Ph.D.Diss. Pushkin, 20 pp.
 30. Ulyanenko L.N., Filipas A.S. and others . 2015: Integrated system of the potato seed planting protection in Kaluga. – *Guarding and quarantine of plants*. 1:23-25.
 31. Vilkova N.A. 2005: Strategy of the agricultural plants guarding from advent sorts insects-phytophages as an example of Colorado insect. – *News of the Plant protection*. 1:3-15.
 32. Yocum G.D. 2001: Differential expression of two HSP70 transcripts in response to cold shock, thermoperiod, and adult diapause in the Colorado potato beetle. – *Insect Physiology*. 47: 1139–1145
 33. Zamalieva F.F. 2013: Potato protection in Tatarstan. – *Guarding and quarantine of plants*. 6:43-45